

Socio-Economic Consequences of Vesico Vaginal Fistula (VVF) On Patients in Katsina and Kano Centres

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ABSTRACT

This research set to study vesico vaginal fistula (VVF) and its socio-economic impacts on patients in Obstetric Fistula Katsina and Kano centres in Northern Nigeria. Much emphasis is often paid on physical injuries of the patient while overlooking the patients' social and economic status of the patients. The study sought to gain a deeper understanding of lived experiences of women with obstetric fistula in the two centers, in order to recommend interventions that would both uplift the patients' moral as well as improve the quality of their life. Thus, prompting this research where survey method was adopted using interview to capture needed information. Purposive sampling technique was adopted to arrive at the sample size of the population. The data collected such as the number, attitude and practices of the VVF patients was analyzed using frequency table with simple percentages. The results indicated 84% to 85% of the patients and their husbands to have attended primary school as the highest educational background and none of them have attended educational level above secondary school. The results also revealed 38% to 40% of the patients to either engage in agriculture or are housewife. Whereas, 33% to 43% of their husband do menial labour or engage in agriculture. Similarly, higher percentage of the patients are from rural areas and have unbalanced nutritional status. Additionally, the finding showed 52% to 55% of the patients and their husbands to be at higher poverty line. However, 62% of the patients received support from both husbands and parents. There should be rigorous and continuous enlighten campaign particularly in the rural areas about the menace VVF/RVF to the women on labour. Government, non-governmental bodies should give more and diversify support; financial food, clothes, pampas and pads to patients in the centers.

1. Introduction

The situation where obstruction occur during labor when the fetus will not fit through the birth canal, and if labor continues for a long period, the blood supply to the compressed tissues is disrupted. Eventually, the injured tissues will necrose and slough away, creating a fistula (Wall, 2014). Wall (2014) defined obstetric fistula as a condition in which the tissues normally separating the vagina from the bladder and/or the rectum are destroyed during obstructed labor.

Obstetric fistula afflicted women often become social outcasts due to stigmatization. It is a major source of public health problem in poor countries. Several million cases of obstetric fistula have been reported to exist in sub-Saharan Africa and south Asia (Lewis, 2012).

In recent years there has been growing concern worldwide about the high maternal morbidity rate in developing countries including Nigeria. Pregnancy and childbirth has for long continued to be a cause of concern, associated with danger and tragedy particularly for the less privileged families most of whom are rural dwellers.

These injuries most commonly in sub-Saharan Africa arise from a crush injury to the vesico vaginal septum during prolonged obstructed labor. These injuries are completely preventable provided the diagnosis of obstructed labor is made early and prompt intervention takes place before extensive ischemia has occurred. However, poorly developed systems of maternal healthcare in West Africa prevent many women from accessing emergency obstetric services in a timely fashion after labor becomes obstructed. This often leads to catastrophic injuries called obstetric fistula. Thus, can be considered largely as a disease of poverty, and West Africa is extremely poor (Wall, 2014).

The problem of vesico vaginal fistula (VVF) was reported to be intense in Nigeria, the most populous country in sub-Saharan Africa, where at least 1%

in every pregnant women die of obstetric complications (WHO & UNICEF, 1996) and where obstructed labor either resulted in maternal death. While women who survive obstructed labor often develop a vesico vaginal fistula (Harrison, 1985).

The accurate number of fistula cases in developing countries is obscured. Several thousands of women are afflicted with this condition worldwide, especially in sub-Saharan Africa. The opportunity for education, economic prosperity and self-determination, are often limited by poverty, illiteracy restricted social roles and above all the enormous burden of suffering caused by VVF (Wall et al, 2005).

2. Social vulnerability

Women with obstetric fistula are affected by social vulnerability as they are undervalued and are often stigmatized. Their awful health problem can make people in such local community to ostracize them. They may feel ashamed, embarrassed, or even fearful (Lewis, 2014).

Numerous literatures have ascribed obstetric fistulas to number of factors in Northern part of Nigeria. Those include early marriage, no or low educational background, high un-employment rate and high poverty line which are often ignored and by extension in cloud despite the untold suffering socio-economic condition of the patients. Thus, prompted this research with the following objectives: 1) Determine the educational background of the patients with VVF in the centres 2) Assess occupational status of VVF patients attending the fistula centres 3) Determine socio-cultural status of the patients in the fistula centres 4) Assess economic status of the patients in the fistula centres 5) other challenges of the patients in the centres.

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3. Materials and Methods

3.1 Study area

Katsina vesico vaginal fistula (VVF) center is located in Babbar ruga, Batagarawa, Katsina state with coordinates of 12°95'16" N 7°57'08" E While, Kano vesico vaginal fistula (VVF) center is situated in Murtala Muhaamad Specialist Hospital Kano with coordinates of 11°59'54.31" N 8°31'24.13" E (Google Earth, 2025).

3.2 Sampling technique and Research instrument

Purposive sampling was used all the fifty eight (58) patients in Katsina and Kano VVF Centres. The oral interview guided by structured questions was conducted to the eight (8) VVF patients in the two National Obstetric Fistula centers fourty eight (48) and ten (10) patients for in Katsina and Kano centre respectively. The interview was used to assess the personal data of the participant, social and economic related to the research questions. The demographic data include; age, The second part referred to selected features on patients' attitude pertaining to socio-economic status such as educational level, marital status, family income, living conditions, nutritional status and types of pregnancy during which the incidence occurred.

3.3 Ethical approval and consent to participate

The interviews were conducted after the participants gave their consent. All the data collection was carried out in line with the principles of the (Declaration of Helsinki, nd; Green, 2009).

3.4 Data Analysis

Data was analyzed and presented in charts and tables containing frequencies and simple percentages using Microsoft Excel to determine the prevalence of patients with VVF and the socio-economic status of the patients attending the fistula centres.

4. Results

4.1 Educational and occupational status of the patients with VVF in the fistula centres

Figure 1: Educational and occupational background of patients and their husbands

Figure 1 showed primary school and traditional education as the highest educational background of the patients represented by 84% and 11% respectively. None of patient attended educational background beyond secondary school. However, those patients who do not attend any form of education have the least percentage of $\leq 5\%$. Other study revealed that majority of the patients have no formal education (Changole, Combs & Kafulafula, 2017). It has further been noted that Ignorance and poor nutrition are factors, often prevalent in low-income communities, which pregnant women more vulnerable to VVF (Poirier & Despires, 2001).

Similarly, patients' husbands recorded primary school and traditional education as their highest educational qualification with 85% and 11% respectively. None of them have higher educational qualifications. Moreover, 4% of the patients do not attend any form of education. This is in line with the previous finding that majority of VVF patients can neither read nor write (Gebretsadik et al., 2023). Thus, due to their educational status bulk majority of the patients or their husbands may not be informed about the causes and consequences of obstetric fistula (Nduka et al., 2023; Mselle et al., 2011).

On occupational status of the patients agriculture and housewife appeared to be the main occupations of the patients with 40% and 38% respectively. This is followed by menial labour and petty trading represented by 17% and 5% respectively. The patients do not engage in white collar job in the study area. This further buttressed the previous research finding that most of patients with obstetric fistula are within low economic background (Diara, 2015).

Menial labour is the main occupations of the patients' husband represented by 43% this is followed by agriculture and petty trading having 33% and 24% respectively. As in patients occupation the white collar job also recorded 0%. There is no direct causal relationship between a husband's occupation and obstetric fistula (Gebretsadik et al., 2023).

4.2 Socio-cultural background of the patients in the centres

Figure 2: Locality of the patients

Figure 2, showed 90% of the patients come from rural areas while 10% of the patients were from rural having. This showed that the cases is more pronounced among the rural populace as corroborated in the previous finding that majority of fistula cases were from rural residences in Guinea (Delamou et al., 2021) and in Ethiopia (Gebretsadik et al., 2023).

Figure 3: Nutritional status of the patients

Figure 3 showed nutritional status where 78% patients with unbalanced diet whereas, 22% of the patients were recorded balanced diet. The patients are especially vulnerable to malnutrition (Shrestha, 2011). Thus, the patients under non-balanced diet category are comparatively higher than the patients with balanced diet. While body size is a vital factor, it often goes

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together with other socioeconomic and health-related issues such as malnutrition.

Figure 6 showed marital statuses of the patients at the point of admission in the center were 91% which is the highest number. It was later reduced to 83% while, 12% were divorced afterward and ≤ 5% were widow. The findings also contrary to [Nduka et al \(2023\)](#) who reported patients being abandoned by families and friends. In Malawi recorded high numbers of divorce among women due to fistula ([Yeakey, Chipeta, Taulo & Tsui, 2009; Changole, Combs & Kafulafula, 2017](#)).

Figure 4: VVF/RVF and age at the wedding

Figure 4 showed 53% of the patients had their wedding between 15 to 17 years range. This is followed by patients who wedded between 18 to 20 years and 12 to 14 years having 17% and 16% respectively. Others have 7% of patients with 21 and above years. Thus, revealed that large numbers of the patients had got married at the age between 15 to 17 years. However, the finding is contrary to the previous which indicated the majority to have got married at the at the age of 14 years ([Changole, Combs & Kafulafula, 2017](#)).

Figure 5: Age of the patients at point of the incidence

Figure 5, revealed age of the patients to be within the range of 21-above years represented at 52% followed by 18-20 years at 36%. The patients were relatively higher at a particular age range 21 above. This investigation were in accordance with findings from research done in Hyderabad Pakistan showed majority of patients were of age group between 20 and 29 years ([Rizwan & Mugha, 2018](#)).

Figure 6: Marital status at the point of admission and now

Figure 7: Index delivery at which fistula occurred

Figure 7 showed index delivery during which fistula occurred where 48% of the patients' is 1st delivery and 12% at 5th delivery. Others 2nd to 4th born and 6th to 12th born have ≤ 9%. The majority of the patients were primiparae (the woman who has delivered a child for the first time). In the previous study majority of the patients had primiparae ([Pierre et al., 2012; Rizwan & Mugha, 2018](#)).

4.3 Economic status of the patients in the centres

Figure 8: Daily Income of patients

Figure 8 showed the daily income of patients where 55% higher poverty line was recorded which is above ₦376.52 per day and 35% extreme poverty line represented by less than ₦376.52 and below per day. Only 10% of the patients' daily income recorded poverty lines of ₦8,800 per day. The kind of occupation to some extent determines the poverty line. The main occupations of the patients and their husbands are agriculture and menial labour respectively. Thus, the occupation may not provide enough to cater for family medical bills. This is in line with previous research finding reported that most of the husbands engage in farming activities as means of their livelihood ([Shrestha, 2011](#)).

Daily income of patients' husbands

Figure 9: Daily Income of patients' husbands

Figure 9 showed the daily income of patients' husbands. The results recorded higher poverty lines above ₦376.52 per day representing 52% and extreme poverty line with 38%. The least is poverty line having 15%. This result corroborated with previous study that majority of the patients' socioeconomic status is low (Poirier & Despires, 2001; Browning, Allsworth, Lewis & Cohen, 2010). Thus, malnutrition is often ascribed to poverty which hinder girls' growth during childhood and adolescence, resulting to smaller and underdeveloped pelvic bone structure (Sambo, 1990; Tsui, Creanga, & Ahmed, 2007; Rizwan & Mughla, 2018).

Support from husband or parent

Figure 10: Support from husband or parent

Figure 10 showed that 62% of the patients received support from both husbands and parents. However, 22% of the patients got support only from their parents. Whereas, 10% of them got support from husband only, the least percentage 2% do not get support from both husband and parent. Higher percentage of the patients received support from both husbands and parents. This is supported by Delamou (2021) most of them received support from their husband/partner. However, contrary to other finding has been reported that fistula patients in Ethiopia were often abandoned by their husbands and stigmatized (Gebretsadik et al., 2023). Most of them received support from their husband/partner during referral after the obstructed labor and later in the search for treatment (Delamou et al., 2021).

4.4 Other problems of the patients in the centres

Other challenges faced by the patients

Figure 11: Other challenges faced by VVF/RVF patients

Figure 11 recorded various challenges ranging other medical related issue 34%, financial or economic issues 28%, and other issues (food, clothes and shelter) with 16% and Social or stigmatization 9%. Whereas, 13% of the patients did not indicate any challenges due to obstetric fistula. Despite the successful repair, previous study indicated that stress-related incontinence occurs in 16–32% of patients because of residual damage (Delamou, 2021). Having uncontrol urine and or feces makes it difficult for individuals to maintain good hygiene and carry on normal social and working lives. Constant uncontrol urination may causes deep ulcerations on the patient's external genitalia, this may extend to the buttocks and thighs, leading to pain and difficulties in movement (Changole, Combs & Kafulafula, 2017).

4. Recommendations

- i. Government should give more emphasis on intensive and continuous enlighten campaign in the rural areas about the causes and consequences of VVF/RVF on pregnant women. This can achieved by forming clubs and associations as well as through the use of various media programs; radio, television, newspapers, drama, films and other social media.
- ii. Federal government and non-governmental organizations in the areas of surgery and medical related treatment in the centers, state and local government should also double their effort in supporting the patients in the centers.
- iii. Patients in the centers have various ranges of problems from financial to economic related issues such as food, clothes, pampas and pads among others. Thus, government, non-governmental bodies including philanthropists can work towards addressing the problem in question.
- iv. The government should encourage micro-credit schemes to empower women economically. This initiative will enable them to access medical care and minimize the economic hardship.

5. Conclusion

Voluminous literatures have ascribed obstetric fistulas to early marriage in Northern part of Nigeria. As well as linking the case to prolong labor, delay in receiving medical attention during obstructive labor, poor state of health care facilities, inadequate material resources, and a lack of trained physicians to address obstetric emergencies. Additionally, the social condition of the patients with VVF are often ignored and by extension in cloud. Thus prompted this is research. Most of the patients are either partake in agriculture activities or just housewife, while majority of their husband earn their livelihood through menial labour or agriculture. Almost all the patients are from rural areas who cannot afford balanced diet. Most of the patients at point of the incidence have age range of 21-above years. The fact that majority of the daily income of patients and their husbands is at higher poverty line. To tackle this situation, government should device sustainable means of alleviating poverty in the country.

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